

Large-Eddy Simulation of an Ejector Integrated in a Rotating Detonation Engine Cycle

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To facilitate the integration of a rotating detonation combustor (RDC) in a turbomachine, adding an ejector downstream of the combustor may be a viable option. The present work examines the performance of an ejector configuration under unsteady inflow conditions representative of an RDC exhaust, using a Large-Eddy Simulation (LES). The RDC exhaust gas is generated at the nozzle exit of the ejector by an adequate choice of inlet axial fluctuation amplitude and frequency. The results along the jet centerline showed that the ejector flow remains in the low supersonic regime before passing through a secondary shock located at the constant-area mixing chamber exit. Mixing between the two flows begins immediately at the confluence and terminates slightly upstream of the secondary shock. The consideration of a theoretical thermodynamic cycle with the calculated ejector revealed that the ejector presence increases specific fuel consumption with respect to a reference cycle without an ejector installed. Entropy generation analysis showed that losses associated with thermal conduction have the most significant impact, followed by viscous dissipation losses. Both originate primarily in the shear layer between the RDC exhaust and the secondary flow. The flow characteristics at the ejector outlet and turbine inlet underline the potential of the ejector to couple the RDC with an axial turbine. Total pressure fluctuations are dampened by 65%, whereas the Mach number and the total temperature distortion are reduced to acceptable levels.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The annual increase in air traffic passengers and stringent emission regulations require the design of high-efficiency, low-emission gas turbines for future aeronautical propulsion applications. However, the optimization of engine components based on the conventional Brayton cycle is reaching a certain degree of saturation¹. This development favors the investigation of different thermodynamic cycles, such as the Fickett-Jacobs cycle. In contrast to the Brayton cycle, the combustion process undergoes a self-pressurization effect due to detonative combustion, which may be exploited for an efficiency gain. One prominent application are rotating detonation combustors (RDCs), in which one or several detonation waves are circulating around an annular combustion chamber². The technology is particularly well-suited for integration with gas turbines due to its frequency in the kHz range³.

One of the most significant challenges in integrated RDC configurations is the interaction of the combustor exhaust gas with downstream components. A series of measurements were conducted in the exhaust plane of an RDC run with natural gas and air by Walters et al.⁴. The flow was found to exhibit significant non-uniformity both spatially and temporally. The exhaust velocity contained an axial component fluctuating between roughly 600 to 1400 m s^{-1} and a circumferential component in the range of -500 to 500 m s^{-1} , with an operating frequency in the low kHz range. Pressure fluctuation amplitudes of up to 200% were measured. In another experimental work, Talukdar et al.⁵ measured similar velocity and pressure fluctuations, at a frequency of several kHz. In the RDC tested by Naples et al.⁶, static pressure fluctuations of the order of 125% were recorded. Using a 2D numerical solver for a hydrogen-air RDC, Klopsch et al.⁷ showed large total pressure and temperature peaks when the oblique shock stemming from the detonation wave passed the combustor outlet plane. The instantaneous outlet flow Mach number was either (1) always subsonic, (2) at times subsonic or supersonic, or (3) at times sonic or supersonic, a result coherent with other numerical and experimental studies⁸.

The described characteristics are fundamentally different from conventional combustor exhausts in turbomachines. Firstly, the mean velocity components and mean total temperature of the RDC exhaust gas are significantly elevated with respect to conventional subsonic turbine inflow, which may have a negative impact on turbine operability and performance⁹. Secondly, the unsteadiness of the exhaust gas has a pronounced effect on turbine operation. Liu et al.¹⁰ conducted a numerical study on the effect of temporal, sinusoidal inlet total pressure and inlet flow

angle fluctuations on the performance of a subsonic turbine stage. The total pressure fluctuations, ranging between 15% and 37.5%, decreased the stage efficiency, and this decrease was more pronounced for lower inlet Mach numbers. At higher inlet Mach numbers, flow angle fluctuations had a more deteriorating effect on efficiency than total pressure fluctuations. Lynch and Boggio¹¹ confirmed in their numerical investigation of a NASA C3X vane geometry under unsteady inflow that with respect to steady reference conditions, total pressure losses are increased across the vane. In addition, they observed incidence angle fluctuations downstream of the vane and an increased unsteadiness of the surface convective heat transfer. The wave decay time did not show an impact on vane performance. St. George et al.¹² compared the performance of an axial turbine under steady and pulsing inflow, using experimental measurements. The tested frequencies were in the tens of Hz, thus not comparable to RDC exhaust frequencies. Nevertheless, the authors identified the corrected mass flow rate and the mass-averaged rotor incidence angle to be the most sensitive driving factors for turbine efficiency, whereas the frequency had only a minor influence.

There exist several strategies to mitigate the possible adverse effects on turbine efficiency and operability. One option is an optimization of conventional subsonic turbines to increase the admissible Mach number and unsteadiness. To avoid unstating, the strategy is only valid for RDC exhaust gas Mach numbers up to 1. In a numerical optimization study based on three-dimensional unsteady simulations, a 21% increase in efficiency compared to the baseline stage could be obtained¹³. The final stage geometry had highly diffusive endwalls, without any change to the airfoil geometry. In another work, an optimization revealed diffusive turbine vanes capable of ingesting transonic flow up to Mach 1¹⁴. A fundamentally different option is the design of a completely new turbine capable of ingesting flow in the low supersonic regime, prohibiting inflow with subsonic velocities. Using the method of characteristics, a supersonic turbine design was presented by Liu et al.¹⁵, where the inlet boundary conditions were extracted from an unsteady RDC simulation. Subsequently, an unsteady simulation was performed for the full turbine stage, where the total pressure loss across the stator and rotor amounted to 23% and 26%. Mushtaq et al.¹⁶ presented a similar approach, coupling a validated mean-line approach to three-dimensional numerical simulations to obtain a new supersonic turbine design. The total-to-total efficiency for the optimized designs reached up to 76%.

The coupling of the RDC with either an optimized subsonic or supersonic turbine does indeed alleviate a number of adverse effects of the exhaust gas on turbine performance. However, neither of the proposed approaches takes into account the subsonic-supersonic mixed velocity regime at

the RDC exhaust, which is typical for a range of operating conditions. One approach that considers this particular fluctuation includes adding an ejector downstream of the RDC and realizing the coupling with a conventional subsonic turbine. In the device, secondary air is entrained that mixes with the unsteady RDC exhaust¹⁷. Naples et al.⁶ investigated such a solution in an experimental study, where ratios of bypass to RDC mass flow rate, defined as the entrainment ratio ω , ranged from zero (i.e. no bypass flow) to approximately 4.0. They observed a substantial reduction of 60-70% in static pressure fluctuations throughout the ejector. The reduction was attributed to the combined effects of pressure wave expansion and energy transfer to the secondary flow within the ejector. In a subsequent work, Paxson and Naples¹⁸ coupled a numerical simulation of an RDC chamber with an analytical model for the downstream ejector. The predictions were then incorporated into a cycle model of the T63 helicopter engine. With an entrainment ratio of 3.0, a turbine adiabatic efficiency of 0.83 was achieved. In another work, where a pulsejet was used to generate unsteady inflow, the ejector effectively reduced RMS pressure fluctuations by an order of magnitude¹⁷. In a recent study¹⁹, a conventional ejector under pulsating inflow was investigated numerically from an aerodynamic perspective, i.e. neglecting the effects of temperature and gas composition. The dampening characteristics observed in previous studies could be confirmed.

In addition to numerical and experimental simulations, the integration of an ejector or mixer in a turbomachine driven by an RDC was investigated via reduced order cycle models. Ji et al.²⁰ assumed a steady, constant-pressure, adiabatic and frictionless mixing model for the ejector and concluded that for minimum pressure loss of the system of RDC and ejector, the entrainment ratio is to be minimized. For the operating point investigated, $\omega = 1.095$, which is lower than the numerically and experimentally tested bypass to RDC mass flow ratios described previously. Qi et al.²¹ found similar results in their RDC cycle analysis. A decrease in entrainment ratio reduced entropy production and primary flow pressure losses in the ejector.

Research on the cycle integration of RDCs with axial turbines using an ejector appears to be relatively sparse, particularly in terms of comprehensive computational analyses. Furthermore, there is a notable absence of design guidelines for these devices. This highlights the necessity for further investigation into this pivotal issue of the incorporation of RDCs into gas turbine systems. To ensure that the involved unsteadiness is accounted for adequately, a Large-Eddy Simulation (LES) is conducted in the current study. A circular ejector configuration under pulsed inflow is investigated, where axial time-magnitude oscillations, mean temperature and gas composition representative of an RDC exhaust gas are considered. The results are utilized to investigate the

internal flow physics and loss mechanisms within the ejector. Moreover, the impact of installing the device in a turbomachinery cycle is assessed. The investigation aims towards an improved understanding of the prospective of integrating an RDC with an ejector in a gas turbine engine.

II. COMPUTATIONAL METHODOLOGY

A. Governing Equations

A numerical simulation of a selected ejector geometry is performed with the compressible, multi-species code AVBP²², which solves the filtered Navier-Stokes equations for Large-Eddy Simulation (LES) on unstructured grids. A non-reacting, multi-species flow is assumed. The fluid state equation is given by the ideal gas law, $P = \rho RT$. The governing equations for mass, species, momentum and energy, introducing a filtering operation of the form $\bar{\rho} \tilde{\psi}(\mathbf{x}) = \overline{\rho \psi(\mathbf{x})} = \int \rho \psi(\mathbf{x}') F(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}') d\mathbf{x}'$ characteristic of LES, read

$$\frac{\partial \bar{\rho}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial (\bar{\rho} \tilde{U}_i)}{\partial x_i} = 0, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial (\bar{\rho} \tilde{Y}_k)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial (\bar{\rho} \tilde{U}_i \tilde{Y}_k)}{\partial x_i} = - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\tilde{J}_{k,i} + J_{k,i}^{SGS} \right), \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial (\bar{\rho} \tilde{U}_i)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial (\bar{\rho} \tilde{U}_i \tilde{U}_j)}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial \bar{P}}{\partial x_j} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\tilde{\tau}_{ij} - \tau_{ij}^{SGS} \right), \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial (\bar{\rho} \tilde{H}_t)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial (\bar{\rho} \tilde{U}_i \tilde{H}_t)}{\partial x_i} = \frac{\partial \bar{P}}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \tilde{q}_i}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial (\tilde{\tau}_{ij} \tilde{U}_i)}{\partial x_j} - \frac{\partial q_i^{SGS}}{\partial x_i} - \frac{\partial (\tau_{ij}^{SGS} \tilde{U}_i)}{\partial x_j}, \quad (4)$$

where the terms q_i , τ_{ij} and $J_{k,i}$ are the heat flux vector, viscous stress tensor and species diffusive flux, respectively. For each term, there is a filtered (denoted by the $\tilde{\cdot}$ -symbol) and subgrid-scale (denoted by the superscript SGS) contribution. The filtered viscous stress tensor $\tilde{\tau}_{ij}$ is obtained by the Newtonian fluid assumption,

$$\tilde{\tau}_{ij} = -\frac{2}{3} \mu \frac{\partial \tilde{U}_k}{\partial x_k} \delta_{ij} + \tilde{S}_{ij} = -\frac{2}{3} \mu \frac{\partial \tilde{U}_k}{\partial x_k} \delta_{ij} + \mu \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{U}_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial \tilde{U}_j}{\partial x_i} \right), \quad (5)$$

where the molecular viscosity μ is calculated using the power law²³. The parameter δ_{ij} is the Heaviside function and \tilde{S}_{ij} is the filtered strain rate. The filtered heat flux vector \tilde{q}_i is given by Fourier's law, with a thermal conductivity calculated by $\lambda = \mu C_p / Pr$, where C_p is the specific heat

capacity and Pr a molecular Prandtl number. The filtered species diffusive fluxes $\tilde{J}_{k,i}$ (k is a species index) are obtained using the Hirschfelder and Curtiss approximation, where a correction velocity is introduced to ensure mass conservation²⁴. The binary species diffusion coefficients needed to compute $\tilde{J}_{k,i}$ are simplified to a single species diffusion coefficient into the mixture, given by $D_k = \mu/(\rho Sc_k)$. The parameter Sc_k is a molecular species Schmidt number. The constants in the power law for viscosity and the molecular Prandtl and Schmidt numbers for the mixture and species are given by the utilized H2-Air chemical mechanism²⁵, and the species sensible enthalpies and heat capacities are extracted from the NIST JANAF database²⁶. The terms denoted by the superscript SGS are not resolved by the numerical grid and require modeling, as is characteristic for LES. The SGS viscous stress tensor τ_{ij}^{SGS} is evaluated by the Wall-Adapting Local Eddy Viscosity (WALE) model²⁷. This model is considered well adapted for wall-bounded flows and has been used in other LES studies of ejectors²⁸. The SGS formulation of the viscous stress tensor relies on the Newtonian fluid assumption (Eq. 5), but the molecular viscosity μ is replaced with a SGS viscosity of the form²⁷

$$\mu^{SGS} = \bar{\rho} (C_W \Delta)^2 \frac{\left(s_{ij}^d s_{ij}^d\right)^{3/2}}{\left(\tilde{S}_{ij} \tilde{S}_{ij}\right)^{5/2} + \left(s_{ij}^d s_{ij}^d\right)^{5/4}}, \quad (6)$$

where \tilde{S}_{ij} is the filtered strain rate, as defined previously, and $C_W = 0.5$ is a model constant. The term s_{ij}^d is obtained by

$$s_{ij}^d = -\frac{2}{3} \tilde{g}_{kk}^2 \delta_{ij} + (\tilde{g}_{ij}^2 + \tilde{g}_{ji}^2), \quad (7)$$

where the terms denoted by \tilde{g} are the squared filtered velocity gradients, which are of the form $\tilde{g}_{ij}^2 = \tilde{g}_{ik} \tilde{g}_{kj}$ (analogously for \tilde{g}_{ji}^2), and $\tilde{g}_{kk}^2 = \tilde{g}_{mk} \tilde{g}_{km}$ ²⁷. The diagonal entries and the term $\partial \tilde{U}_k / \partial x_k$ are neglected in the formulation of the SGS viscous stress tensor in AVBP. The SGS heat and diffusive fluxes, q_i^{SGS} and $J_{k,i}^{SGS}$, are approximated by a gradient assumption utilizing SGS transport coefficients. The SGS thermal conductivity is given by $\lambda^{SGS} = \mu^{SGS} C_p / Pr^{SGS}$, where Pr^{SGS} was set to 0.89²⁹. The SGS species diffusion coefficient is calculated by $D_k^{SGS} = \mu^{SGS} / (\rho Sc_k^{SGS})$, where Sc_k^{SGS} is constant for all species and set to 0.7²⁹.

A two-step Taylor-Galerkin finite element scheme, which is 3rd order space and 4th order time accurate, is utilized to discretize the convective fluxes³⁰. The implementation in AVBP is based on the cell-vertex formulation²². For the viscous fluxes, a finite element scheme in a vertex-centered

formulation is utilized for discretization. To avoid dispersive errors related to the use of centered schemes, artificial scalar diffusion based on the sensor developed by Colin³¹ is utilized. Moreover, large gradients related to potential shock formulation are not dissipated well by the viscous scheme at elevated Reynolds numbers, which may introduce numerical difficulties in LES. To mitigate this issue, artificial diffusivity is added in regions of high gradients to the diagonal entries of the filtered viscous stress tensor (Eq. 5) according to the model proposed by Cook and Cabot³². For computational affordability, the LES presented in this work is wall-modeled, employing a logarithmic law-of-the-wall³³. All walls are considered adiabatic.

B. Domain Setup

The investigated ejector geometry is presented in Fig. 1, where a converging-diverging nozzle is employed to generate the RDC exhaust gas, a strategy previously utilized in a similar study¹⁹. As a result of this modeling, the nozzle exit section is considered representative of the RDC exhaust, and the term "RDC exit" refers to the primary nozzle exit at station 4 throughout the conducted study. The circular cross-sectional area at station 4 is matched with the exhaust section of an existing, annular RDC at TU Berlin¹. The primary flow inlet termed 4' here has no formal relevance in the calculation. After the primary flow passes through $x/d_4 = 0$, where d_4 is the diameter at station 4, the secondary flow is admitted into the device and mixing between both flows initiates. Once the flow has passed through the constant-area mixing chamber and the diffuser, it enters a fictive turbine at station 41, which is located upstream of the domain outlet 41'. Consequently, the area of interest, and where most of the analysis will be carried out, is from station 4 (nozzle exit/RDC exit) to station 41 (turbine inlet), as indicated by dark color in Fig. 1. The configuration is an up-scaled version of the conventional ejector design by Kracik and Dvorak³⁴, whose pure aerodynamic behavior under unsteady inflow was studied previously¹⁹.

C. Boundary Conditions

Inlet and outlet boundaries are described by Navier-Stokes Characteristic Boundary Conditions (NSCBC), a standard boundary formulation for LES³⁵. At the primary inlet 4', axial velocity and static temperature are enforced; total pressure and total temperature are prescribed at the secondary inlet 14³⁶, and static pressure is imposed at the domain outlet 41'³⁷. For the secondary flow inlet

FIG. 1. Main geometrical parameters and indexing of the studied ejector configuration.

properties, pressure and temperature were the result of a simple thermodynamic cycle calculation, which will be detailed in section III C. The primary flow is considered burned gas from an RDC operated with hydrogen-air, where $Y_{N_2,4'} = 0.745$ and $Y_{H_2O,4'} = 0.255^1$. The secondary flow is air, with $Y_{N_2,14} = 0.77$ and $Y_{O_2,14} = 0.23$.

To generate RDC exhaust characteristics at the nozzle exit, a sinusoidal acoustic pulsation is imposed at the primary inlet using the formalism from Daviller et al.³⁸. The acoustic pulsation generates a velocity perturbation of the form $u = \bar{u} + A \sin(2\pi ft)$, where \bar{u} is the mean velocity, A and f are amplitude and frequency of the pulsation, respectively. Since the inlet perturbation is enforced as an acoustic wave, pressure is pulsated accordingly. The amplitude $A_{4'}$ and mean velocity $u_{4'}$ are selected to ensure a transonic pulsating flow at the nozzle exit, and the frequency is set to $f_{4'} = 8$ kHz, which is an estimation based on the study of Stempfll et al.³⁹. A similar pulsating strategy with a sinusoidal signal to model the RDC exhaust has been used in other studies⁴⁰. The transverse components of the RDC exhaust flow are neglected in this study. The primary flow static temperature was fixed at 2330 K, which was approximated based on existing RDC studies^{39,41}. The boundary values imposed are summarized in Table I.

D. Initialization and Computational Procedure

The computation was initialized on a coarse grid without any primary inlet pulsations, i.e. $A_{4'}$ and $f_{4'}$ set to zero (all other boundary values from Table I unchanged). To avoid large gradients in this phase of the computation, artificial viscosity (AV) with values approximately five orders of magnitude larger than the molecular viscosity of the studied flow, was employed. Once the mass flow rates through the domain boundaries were converged, the computation was interrupted. Subsequently, the solution was interpolated on the fine grid used in this study (section II E), and the

TABLE I. Boundary values imposed for the investigated ejector configuration.

Primary Inlet (4')	$\bar{u}_{4'}$	198.32 m s^{-1}
	$A_{4'}$	135 m s^{-1}
	$f_{4'}$	8 kHz
	$T_{s4'}$	2330 K
	$Y_{H_2O,4'}$	0.255
	$Y_{N_2,4'}$	0.745
Secondary Inlet (14)	P_{t14}	506.625 kPa
	T_{t14}	456.38 K
	$Y_{N_2,14}$	0.77
	$Y_{O_2,14}$	0.23
Outlet (41')	P_{s41}	495 kPa

AV model was changed following the previously introduced sensor of Colin³¹, which decreased AV values by several orders of magnitude, as is required for LES. Once the mass flow rate variation through the domain boundaries was below 5%, the computation was considered steady-state. With a convective time of $t_c = 0.00158$ s, the computed physical time necessary to obtain this steady-state solution from the initial, large-AV flow field, was roughly $3.2 t_c$.

Using the steady-state LES solution now as the initial flow field, the pulsated computation was launched with $A_{4'}$ and $f_{4'}$ set according to Table I and for a physical time of 0.01 s, roughly $6.3 t_c$ and corresponding to 80 periods of the fluctuation. The Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy number was set to 0.7, resulting in a mean timestep size of 2.95×10^{-8} s. The value of 0.7 is recommended for the TTG4A scheme introduced previously⁴². The full computations were conducted using 32 AMD nodes, each with 256 GB RAM and 128 cores, leading to roughly 27,000 CPU hours per convective time.

E. Computational Grid

Although challenging in LES since the resolution acts as an implicit filter⁴³, a grid sensitivity study has been conducted, where three grids with increasing resolution were tested. The computations for the grid size analysis were done using a steady-state solution. To keep the computational

cost affordable, the calculations for the grid size analysis study were conducted on periodic sectors of 30 deg instead of the full 360 deg configuration. Since the presence of the axis introduces erroneous predictions of turbulence in LES⁴⁴, the reduced domain size is deemed suitable for the purpose of grid size analysis only. The three grids investigated are fully tetrahedral and consist of 12,421,587 (termed 12m), 24,358,473 (termed 24m) and 47,660,298 (termed 48m) elements, respectively. In Fig. 2, the leading shock position in the primary nozzle, obtained by a time-averaged field of the density gradient magnitude, is compared between the selected grids. The white line indicates Mach unity. The leading shock position governs the flow characteristics at the nozzle exit, which are an important quantity in the present work. Qualitatively, sufficient agreement is evident between the medium, 24m mesh and the finest, 48m mesh. In addition, static pressure along a horizontal line of $y = d_4/2$ between close to the nozzle exit at $x/d_4 = 0.5$ and the domain outlet were extracted from a time-averaged solution. Figure 3 shows the results for all three grids tested, where predictions agree well between the 24m and 48m grids, relative to the coarsest, 12m grid.

FIG. 2. Qualitative comparison of flow fields in the nozzle exit region for different grid resolutions, with an isoline of Mach unity.

Following the described analysis, the sizing employed for the 24m grid is chosen as appropriate and was applied to a full 360 deg configuration of the studied ejector. The final grid retained has 277,880,278 tetrahedral cells. The reduced cell count with respect to the theoretical, multiplied 30 deg sector cell count of the 24m grid stems from the merging of two cell layers on the ejector centerline in the 360 deg configuration. Figure 4 shows an overview and several zoomed sections of the final, full 360 deg grid. Cell sizing at the nozzle exit is set to 210 μm , providing 15 cells in vertical direction at the lip between primary and secondary flow channels. Throughout the mixing chamber (with the exception of the refined near-wall region), cell size is set to 0.9 mm, and starts

FIG. 3. Comparison of static pressure predictions along a horizontal line of $y = d_4/2$ for different grid resolutions.

increasing towards its exit. Through the diffuser and the constant-area outlet section, cell size increases linearly. The dimensionless wall distance y^+ is of the order of 60 along the secondary inlet channel and the constant-area mixing chamber; it increases throughout the diffuser up to 85. The values are considered reasonable for wall-modeled LES⁴². The relative grid sizing is very similar to a previous LES of an ejector under unsteady inflow, where a validation with experimental data showed good agreement¹⁹.

FIG. 4. Overview of selected grid, with zoomed snapshots in the nozzle exit region, along the mixing chamber wall and along the diffuser.

To further confirm the suitability of the selected grid, the filtered turbulent kinetic energy was

compared to the total turbulent kinetic energy which includes the subgrid-scale contribution. The metric is termed the Quality Index (QI), as defined by Celik et al.⁴⁵, where a value of 0.8 is an accepted lower threshold⁴⁶. Figure 5 shows QI, with a white isoline of QI = 0.8. Within the constant-area mixing zone, values over 95% are observed, whereas the decreasing resolution throughout the diffuser reduces QI to roughly 85% at the diffuser exit. Downstream of the considered turbine inlet (see Fig. 1), the grid was derefined significantly to evacuate the unsteady flow smoothly from the domain. Within the secondary flow channel, the grid resolution is coarser to save computational resources. The average QI value throughout the domain volume was 0.91. The analysis confirms that the relevant region of the domain has a sufficiently high QI⁴⁶.

FIG. 5. Quality Index (QI) for the selected grid and operating condition, as defined by Celik et al.⁴⁵, with a white isoline of QI = 0.8.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Comparison of Nozzle Exit Flow to Typical RDC Exhaust

The flow characteristics at the primary nozzle exit, station 4, are analyzed to evaluate the degree of representation of a typical RDC exhaust. Figure 6 shows the total pressure of the flow on the jet centerline exiting the primary nozzle, in comparison to numerical predictions^{7,47} in the RDC exit plane. To ensure that the comparison is coherent, P_{t4} was normalized by its respective time-averaged value. The total pressure fluctuation of the flow generated at the nozzle exit matches sufficiently well with the mentioned studies, both in frequency and amplitude, with an averaged relative error of 18%.

Figure 7 presents a comparative analysis of total temperature predictions on the jet centerline with the same numerical studies. As for the total pressure, numerical predictions available in literature agree sufficiently well, both in amplitude and frequency, with the RDC exhaust generated at the nozzle exit in this study. The averaged relative error was 11%. It is noteworthy that the

FIG. 6. Jet centerline total pressure generated at the nozzle exit of the ejector (P_{t4}) in comparison to typical RDC exit numerical predictions.

total temperature fluctuation was not explicitly imposed at the primary inlet 4' (as described in section II C); it is rather a result of the unsteady shock motion within the diverging part of the nozzle.

FIG. 7. Jet centerline total temperature generated at the nozzle exit of the ejector (T_{t4}) in comparison to typical RDC exit numerical predictions.

B. Dynamic Flow Field Analysis

1. General Flow Field Description

Figures 8 to 11 show a time sequence of an instantaneous Q-criterion isosurface colored by vorticity magnitude along the ejector mixing chamber and diffuser downstream of the primary nozzle exit (for $0 < x/d_4 < 15$). In addition, a horizontal cut with a density gradient magnitude field is depicted in the x-y plane. In the x-z plane, the nitrogen mass fraction Y_{N_2} is shown, with a white isoline of Mach = 1. The four snapshots constitute a single period of the imposed fluctuation with a duration of $\Delta t = 1/f_4 = 1.25 \times 10^{-4}$ s. The isoline of Mach = 1 indicates that the nozzle exit flow is periodically changing its velocity regime from subsonic to supersonic and vice versa. The nozzle exit jet diameter changes accordingly with this fluctuation, as evident when comparing Figs. 8 and 10. Close to the nozzle exit, larger turbulent structures form along the shear layer; further downstream, the jet shear layer starts interacting with the boundary layer, leading to a formation of turbulent structures towards the wall and away from the centerline. Qualitatively, the mixing distance seems relatively unaffected by the imposed fluctuations. Shock diamonds close to the nozzle exit are visible in the density gradient magnitude fields, although much less pronounced than in supersonic jets; an expected effect since the jet remains in the low supersonic velocity regime. In addition, a secondary shock is permanently located at the end of the constant-area mixing chamber at $x/d_4 = 11.75$.

Figure 12 shows a plot of the instantaneous Mach number along the jet centerline for the same period than previously. Additionally, the time-averaged jet centerline Mach number and its respective two-dimensional field are displayed. The typical transonic character of an RDC exhaust signal is well represented by the nozzle exit Mach number, which varies between approximately 0.5 and 1.35. The secondary flow remains in the subsonic regime along its channel upstream of the mixing chamber, as evident from the time-averaged Mach number field. Throughout the mixing chamber, the Mach number peaks are convected downstream over time, where they seem to converge towards a Mach number in the low supersonic regime. A strong flow non-uniformity is apparent in the instantaneous plots, with local maxima and minima at 1.7 and 0.8, respectively. Due to the boundary layer acting as an aerodynamic convergent, both subsonic and supersonic portions of the flow tend to Mach unity along the constant-area mixing chamber (characteristic of transonic Fanno flow⁴⁸). This process continuously reduces the Mach number fluctuation amplitude, as has

FIG. 8. Nitrogen mass fraction Y_{N_2} (x-z plane), isosurface of the Q-criterion colored by vorticity, and density gradient magnitude (x-y plane) at $t = 0.25\Delta t$.

FIG. 9. Nitrogen mass fraction Y_{N_2} (x-z plane), isosurface of the Q-criterion colored by vorticity, and density gradient magnitude (x-y plane) at $t = 0.5\Delta t$.

been observed in studies investigating the coupling of an RDC with a converging nozzle⁵. From

FIG. 10. Nitrogen mass fraction Y_{N_2} (x-z plane), isosurface of the Q-criterion colored by vorticity, and density gradient magnitude (x-y plane) at $t = 0.75\Delta t$.

FIG. 11. Nitrogen mass fraction Y_{N_2} (x-z plane), isosurface of the Q-criterion colored by vorticity, and density gradient magnitude (x-y plane) at $t = \Delta t$.

a time-averaged point of view, the flow remains in the low supersonic regime until it undergoes

transition through a secondary shock at $x/d_4 = 11.75$. Beyond $x/d_4 > 11.75$, the absolute Mach number decreases further until reaching the turbine inlet.

FIG. 12. Instantaneous (over Δt) and time-averaged Mach number predictions along the ejector centerline, with a time-averaged Mach number field.

Figure 13 shows the time-averaged total and static pressure and temperature along the jet centerline together with time-averaged fields. The data indicates a pressure and temperature drop along the mixing chamber. The total pressure remains unchanged up until $x/d_4 = 5$ before decreasing. The drop in total quantities for $x/d_4 < 11.75$ is not related to a decrease in Mach number (see Fig. 12), but is rather caused by a decrease in static pressure and temperature, as highlighted in Fig. 13. The static quantities confirm the presence of density gradients related to shock diamond structures for $x/d_4 < 2$, as observed previously in instantaneous quantities. Following the ideal jump conditions for a normal shock wave⁴⁸, the total temperature remains constant whereas total pressure drops and static pressure increases through the shock at $x/d_4 = 11.75$. The small increase in total pressure at approximately $x/h_4 = 12$ is a local phenomenon, as quantities were extracted on the jet centerline only. The total temperature decreases by roughly 40%, and total pressure drops by approximately 30% between RDC exit and turbine inlet, with potential effects on performance. Integrated ejector performance is further analyzed in section III C.

FIG. 13. Time-averaged total and static pressure and temperature predictions along the ejector centerline, with time-averaged fields of T_t and P_t .

2. Mass Flow Rates

The imposed acoustic pulsation at the primary inlet boundary leads to significant mass flux fluctuations in the computational domain. Fig. 14 depicts the instantaneous RDC exit mass flux J_4 , the secondary inlet mass flux J_{14} and the turbine inlet mass flux J_{41} . Additionally, the instantaneous entrainment ratio $\omega = \dot{m}_{14}/\dot{m}_4$ is shown. At the RDC exit, the time-averaged mass flux amounted to $502 \text{ kg s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$, which corresponds to a reduced flow rate of $\dot{m}_4 \sqrt{T_{t4}}/P_{t4} = 5.3 \times 10^{-5} \text{ kg} \sqrt{\text{K}}/\text{s}/\text{Pa}$. This value is comparable to experimental ($\approx 4.9 \times 10^{-5} \text{ kg} \sqrt{\text{K}}/\text{s}/\text{Pa}$)⁴⁹ and numerical ($\approx 5.6 \times 10^{-5} \text{ kg} \sqrt{\text{K}}/\text{s}/\text{Pa}$)⁷ findings. The RDC exit signal shows no evidence of peak-to-peak variations, and the imposed frequency of 8 kHz is well recovered. As assessed in a previous study¹⁹, the pulsation of the primary flow causes a significant perturbation of the secondary mass flux. This perturbation is due to the pressure variations in the primary jet causing local changes in secondary flow entrainment. At the turbine inlet, the mass flux signal amplitude is considerably smaller than at the RDC exit. The frequency of 8 kHz appears unchanged. From the mass flux characteristics, it is concluded that the main frequency of the pulsation is retained throughout unsteady ejector operation, which is coherent with previous studies¹⁹. Nevertheless, some peak-to-peak variations are visible in the turbine inlet mass flux, which suggest a signal distribution

over a wider range of frequencies than at the RDC exit. This claim will be further investigated in section III C. The instantaneous entrainment ratio varies between roughly 0.8 and 3.2, with a time-averaged value of 1.44. The main driver for entrainment ratio fluctuations is the primary flow rate, i.e. ω peaks locally at local minima of J_4 .

FIG. 14. Integrated RDC exit (J_4), secondary inlet (J_{14}) and turbine inlet (J_{41}) mass fluxes, and local entrainment ratio $\omega = \dot{m}_{14}/\dot{m}_4$.

3. Instantaneous Velocity Profiles

In an attempt to characterize the transport of momentum through the domain, instantaneous axial velocity profiles are analyzed at several axial planes, as shown in Fig. 15. The four traces over Δt in each plane plot correspond to a single fluctuation period. Close to the RDC exit at $x/d_4 = 1$, axial velocity peaks amount to 1200 ms^{-1} for $t = 0.75\Delta t$. The snapshots at $t = 0.25\Delta t$ and $t = 0.5\Delta t$ are similar in magnitude, whereas the minimum peak is obtained at $t = \Delta t$. The profiles are close to symmetric with respect to the jet centerline, although they differ from conventional ejector velocity profiles which are typically bell-shaped close to the nozzle exit²⁸. At this axial plane, primary and secondary flow are clearly distinguishable. Further downstream at $x/d_4 = 3$, the symmetry has vanished and the primary flow peak is less regular, an indication that both

flows are interacting and mixing. Similar irregular characteristics are evident at $x/d_4 = 6$, where primary and secondary flows are difficult to distinguish. At the end of the constant-area mixing chamber, $x/d_4 = 11.75$, axial velocity profiles are more spatially uniform relative to upstream axial planes, indicating that mixing has terminated. Through the diffuser, the mean flow velocity reduces considerably. Moreover, fluctuations decrease further and a seemingly steady flow is obtained at $x/d_4 = 15.5$. For all planes within $x/d_4 \leq 11.75$, the mean value of the axial velocity does not change considerably, which is in line with Fig. 12.

FIG. 15. Instantaneous (over Δt) axial velocity profiles along the ejector mixing chamber ($1 < x/d_4 < 15.5$).

4. Quantification of Mixing

To characterize the mixing process between primary and secondary flow, a mixing efficiency metric is defined⁵⁰

$$\eta_m = 1 - \sqrt{\frac{\sigma^2}{\sigma_{max}^2}}, \quad (8)$$

where σ^2 is the variance of one of the species mass fractions of the mixture given by

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{i=1}^K (Y_i - Y_{opt})^2. \quad (9)$$

In Eq. 8, σ_{max}^2 is the maximum variance. The mass fraction Y_i is the pointwise extracted mass fraction along a given axial plane and K is the total number of points in that axial plane. The parameter Y_{opt} is the optimum mass fraction obtained under ideal mixing. The metric has been extracted for the mass fraction of water vapor, Y_{H_2O} (with $Y_{H_2O,opt} = 0.101$ for the calculated time-averaged primary and secondary flow rates), along a number of axial planes in the mixing chamber and diffuser, both instantaneously over Δt and time-averaged. The results are shown in

Fig. 16. At the RDC exit, the mixing efficiency η_m is zero since the maximum variance σ_{max}^2 is equal to the obtained variance σ^2 . Mixing initiates instantly, a result of the primary jet velocity regime being either subsonic or in the low supersonic regime, thus with a relatively small transverse velocity gradient with respect to the secondary flow (in contrast to conventional ejectors). Rapid initiation of the mixing process is a desired characteristic in an RDC - ejector system, since a decrease in mixing length allows a decrease in total ejector length. The mixing efficiency follows an approximately linear trajectory until $x/d_4 = 6$, upon which its gradient decreases. Further downstream, η_m reaches a saturated value close to $\eta_m = 1$. Defining $\eta_m = 0.9$ as fully mixed, the time-averaged mixing length is determined as $x/d_4 = 11$ for the investigated configuration. Instantaneous mixing efficiencies show considerable differences along the mixing chamber in the region $x/d_4 < 9$ which decrease significantly further downstream, indicating that the mixing length is largely unaffected by the primary flow fluctuations (as previously observed qualitatively in Figs. 8 to 11). This is a beneficial characteristic in an integrated RDC - ejector configuration.

FIG. 16. Instantaneous and time-averaged mixing efficiency η_m for the investigated ejector configuration.

C. Performance Analysis

Following the assessment of the ejector dynamic flow field, its performance is now assessed with respect to a number of objectives. The performance analysis is conducted in three separate steps. Firstly, the indirect impact of the calculated ejector on a simple thermodynamic cycle with an RDC is assessed, and global performance parameters are evaluated. Secondly, losses within

the ejector itself are investigated, and potential areas of improvement are identified. Thirdly, the ejector exhaust flow at station 41 is analyzed and related to conventional turbine inlet flow characteristics. The ensemble of these analyses characterizes the potential of the investigated ejector configuration to be integrated with an RDC in a gas turbine engine.

1. Global Cycle Performance

In order to evaluate the impact of the ejector on global thermodynamic cycle performance, a theoretical simple cycle design is considered, as shown in Fig. 17. The layout is coherent with literature²⁰.

FIG. 17. Cycle layout with the proposed integrated RDC - ejector system.

Ambient air is ingested and subsequently compressed in the first compressor stage from station 1 to 2. Thereafter, the air mass flow is split, where one part, the primary flow, is admitted into the RDC as an oxidant for combustion (station 3 to 4). Neglecting losses, $P_{t3} = P_{t2}$ and $T_{t3} = T_{t2}$ but $\dot{m}_3 < \dot{m}_2$ since only a portion of the total mass flow rate enters the RDC. The remaining air bypasses the combustion chamber and is fed into the ejector as the secondary flow at station 14, where $P_{t14} = P_{t2}$ and $T_{t14} = T_{t2}$ but $\dot{m}_{14} < \dot{m}_2$. The investigated ejector is located downstream of the RDC, with the RDC exhaust gas at station 4, the secondary flow at station 14 and the turbine inlet at station 41. The indexing is coherent with Fig. 1. The flow at station 41 is then expanded in a turbine and exhausted in a converging-diverging nozzle.

The specific fuel consumption is selected as a representative performance metric, and reads for the proposed cycle⁵¹

$$sfc = \frac{FAR}{\Delta H_{t,u}} = \frac{FAR}{\dot{m}C_p(T_{t41} - T_{t9})}, \quad (10)$$

where $\Delta H_{t,u}$ is the usable work and FAR is the fuel-to-air ratio in the RDC. Equation 10 shows that a high temperature at the turbine inlet at station 41 improves specific fuel consumption. The presented equation does not contain the entrainment ratio ω , although it is implicitly involved in T_{t41} ⁵². Ji et al.²⁰ showed in their cycle analysis that an increase in ω decreases T_{t41} for a given compressor pressure ratio. Consequently, sfc increases with increasing ω .

To provide a link with characteristic performance parameters of RDCs, a pressure gain metric is also adapted. Generally, the pressure gain is calculated as $P_{t,exit}/P_{t,inj} - 1$, where $P_{t,exit}$ is the total pressure at the RDC exit and $P_{t,inj}$ is the oxidizer injection total pressure⁵³. For the presented cycle, the metric is extended to include the ejector,

$$\eta_{pg} = \frac{P_{t41}}{P_{t2}} - 1. \quad (11)$$

A simplified cycle calculation is now employed, using the following assumptions: Ambient conditions are atmospheric, all expansion and compression processes are considered isentropic, and the compressor pressure ratio is equal to 5. The RDC itself is treated as a blackbox, with inlet conditions at station 3 given by the cycle calculation, and exit conditions given by extracting results from the ejector computation at station 4. Results at station 41 are given by the performed LES; all other values are calculated using the simplified cycle assumptions outlined above. To determine the impact of the ejector, an equivalent RDC cycle without an ejector present is additionally considered for comparison. In that case, the expansion in the turbine is done directly from state 4 instead of state 41 (i.e. quantities with the index 41 in Eqs. 10 and 11 are replaced by index 4).

The defined parameters are now applied to the time-averaged predictions obtained in the LES of the ejector. Quantities in planes 4, 14 and 41 were massflow-averaged. Figures 18 and 19 show a T_t - ΔS and a P_t - v_t diagram for the investigated cycles. In the cycle without ejector, the turbine expansion work increases, which increases the usable enthalpy $\Delta H_{t,u}$ for a given compressor pressure ratio. Increasing $\Delta H_{t,u}$ has a direct impact on specific fuel consumption: For the RDC and ejector configuration, sfc was approximately 30% higher than without the ejector installed (assuming equal values of FAR, \dot{m} and C_p in Eq. 10). The pressure gain of the two cycles is $\eta_{pg} = 0.083$ and $\eta_{pg}^{ne} = 0.654$ for the RDC and ejector and the no-ejector cycles, respectively. It is worth noting that the pressure gain of the cycle without ejector is an optimistic estimation, although similar values have been established in other studies⁵⁴.

The evaluation of sfc and η_{pg} underlines one of the key challenges currently limiting the application of RDCs in turbomachinery. Without any ejector in place, relatively good global per-

FIG. 18. Total temperature-entropy diagram for the proposed thermodynamic cycle and the no-ejector RDC cycle.

FIG. 19. Total pressure-specific volume diagram for the proposed thermodynamic cycle and the no-ejector RDC cycle.

formance parameters are indeed obtained. Installing an ejector considerably reduces global performance. However, for the no-ejector cycle, the RDC exit flow directly enters the turbine, with possibly significant performance penalties⁶ that are not considered in the cycle diagrams. The characteristics based on this simplified steady-state global cycle analysis point towards an optimized, low-loss ejector as a key element in the turbomachinery integration of RDCs.

To take into account the unsteadiness of the RDC exhaust flow, a time-dependent evaluation of the global performance is conducted in addition to the steady-state analysis. To this end, η_{pg} is extracted for ten instantaneous snapshots at station 4 and 41 within a single period of the fluctuation (with the duration of Δt). Figure 20 shows instantaneous values of the pressure gain η_{pg} . Furthermore, traces of massflow-averaged, instantaneous total pressure P_t at the RDC exit and the turbine inlet are presented. The results show a significant influence of the unsteady pulsation on global cycle performance. The amplitude of pressure fluctuations is considerably reduced between stations 4 and 41, which is a beneficial characteristic for axial turbine inflow (a detailed unsteadiness analysis is presented in subsequent sections). However, even with an ejector in place as an intermediate component between RDC and axial turbine, a considerable influence of the unsteadiness on cycle performance is asserted.

FIG. 20. Instantaneous pressure gain η_{pg} , massflow-averaged total pressure at the RDC exit P_{t4} , and at the turbine inlet P_{t41} over a single period of the fluctuation.

2. Entropy Generation Analysis

The preceding analysis, where the ejector was integrated in a theoretical thermodynamic cycle with an RDC, showed significant performance penalties compared to a reference cycle without an ejector in place. However, these penalties have not been related to specific loss phenomena on a

local scale within the ejector. Identifying these mechanisms is a crucial step in increasing ejector performance in future analyses.

One approach to enable such identification is the method of entropy generation⁵⁵. Arbel et al.⁵² have shown for a 1D air-air ejector that the irreversible entropy generation rate within the device is equivalent to the deviation of the outlet thermodynamic state from its ideal, isentropic state. Sierra-Pallares et al.⁵⁶ applied the method to three different ejector configurations to identify the most advantageous design. Thus, estimating the entropy generation rate is deemed a suitable approach to estimate loss generation in the ejector. Neglecting radiation and any coupling effects, and applying the expression in an LES context, the time-averaged irreversible entropy generation rate \dot{S}_{gen} for the studied ejector configuration reads^{55,57}

$$\dot{S}_{gen} = \Pi_{hc} + \Pi_{vd} + \Pi_{sd}, \quad (12)$$

$$\Pi_{hc} = \frac{\lambda + \lambda^{SGS}}{\tilde{T}^2} \overline{\left(\frac{\partial \tilde{T}}{\partial x_i} \right)^2}, \quad (13)$$

$$\Pi_{vd} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\mu + \mu^{SGS}}{\tilde{T}} \overline{\left(\frac{\partial \tilde{U}_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial \tilde{U}_j}{\partial x_i} - \frac{2}{3} \frac{\partial \tilde{U}_i}{\partial x_j} \delta_{ij} \right) \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{U}_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial \tilde{U}_j}{\partial x_i} \right)}, \quad (14)$$

$$\Pi_{sd} = - \overline{\sum_{k=1}^N \left(\tilde{J}_{k,i} + J_{k,i}^{SGS} \right) \frac{R_k}{\tilde{X}_k} \frac{\partial \tilde{X}_k}{\partial x_i}}, \quad (15)$$

where Π_{hc} , Π_{vd} and Π_{sd} are heat conduction losses, viscous dissipation losses, and species diffusion losses, respectively.

Figure 21 shows the entropy generation terms defined in Eqs. 13 to 15 along the ejector. In general, losses are located in the shear layer, the boundary layer, the secondary shock region and in the near-wall region of the diffuser. However, the peak values of all three loss terms appear to be most significant in the shear layer between the primary and secondary flow. Along the primary jet centerline, losses remain low until the end of the jet core zone. In the fully developed region, heat conduction losses Π_{hc} and viscous dissipation losses Π_{vd} start decreasing at around 2/3 of the mixing chamber length, although Π_{hc} drops more rapidly than Π_{vd} downstream of the mixing chamber. A separation region induced by the diffuser leads to a local increase in Π_{vd} ; the influence of the separation on Π_{hc} and Π_{sd} is negligible. Species diffusion losses Π_{sd} start decreasing towards the end of the mixing chamber, attaining much smaller absolute values than

Π_{hc} and Π_{vd} . Very small values of Π_{sd} are present downstream of the mixing chamber, which is coherent with the negligible deviation of η_m from unity for $x/d_4 > 11$ (see Fig. 16).

FIG. 21. Entropy generation rate terms related to viscous dissipation (Π_{vd}), heat conduction (Π_{hc}) and species diffusion (Π_{sd}).

In order to quantify the effect on ejector performance, each loss term is volume-integrated over the relevant domain volume (as indicated in Fig. 1). The different contributions are outlined in Fig. 22: Approximately 64% of the overall loss budget are due to heat conduction losses, whereas viscous dissipation losses amount to roughly 33%. Species diffusion losses are 2.3% of the integrated total losses. The results show that losses in the ejector are mostly a result of velocity and thermal gradients ($\Pi_{vd} = f(\partial \tilde{U}_i / \partial x_j), f(\partial \tilde{U}_j / \partial x_i)$ and $\Pi_{hc} = f(\partial \tilde{T} / \partial x_i)$); species gradients exhibit only a minor impact. The limited impact of losses associated with species diffusion can be attributed to the high nitrogen content in both secondary and primary flow ($Y_{N2,14} = 0.77$, $Y_{N2,4'} = 0.745$, see Tab. I) which limits the value of $\partial \tilde{X}_k / \partial x_i$.

The assessment of different loss terms underlines that for maximizing ejector performance, primarily heat conduction and viscous dissipation losses need to be minimized. However, specific phenomena that are responsible for loss generation and thus best mitigated to achieve performance maximization are not yet identified. Therefore, in the following, an attempt is made to establish a link between loss generation and the physical phenomena occurring within the device. The

FIG. 22. Contributions of volume-integrated loss terms Π_{vd} , Π_{hc} and Π_{sd} on the overall loss budget.

evaluation is done by spatially isolating four regions of interest, as shown in Fig. 23. The four physical phenomena contributing to loss generation include the shear layer in the mixing chamber, the boundary layer, the observed secondary shock and the diffuser-induced separation region. The region of interest that accounts for boundary-layer induced losses was defined after measuring the boundary layer thickness. However, due to the interaction between shear layer and boundary layer, starting downstream of roughly $x/d_4 \approx 2$ (see Figs. 8 to 11), both physical phenomena are contributing to losses in that region.

FIG. 23. Regions of interest for entropy generation terms extraction (BL = boundary layer, Sec. Shock = secondary shock, Sep. = diffuser-induced separation).

The relative contributions per specific phenomena after volume integration of the regions of interest are shown in Figure 24. Losses generated outside of the four investigated regions of interest throughout the domain are referred to as "Other". In general, a large majority of total loss contributions are concentrated in the shear layer along the mixing chamber. For Π_{hc} and Π_{sd} , contributions outside the shear layer are negligible. Viscous dissipation losses Π_{vd} originate pri-

marily in the shear layer (approximately 68%), followed by the separation induced in the diffuser (roughly 13%). The influence of the boundary layer and of other regions that were not explicitly extracted is of the order of 10%, respectively. The non-negligible value of Π_{vd} in regions outside of the selected regions of interest is coherent with Fig. 21, where Π_{vd} is not as low downstream of the diffuser as the other two loss terms. The influence of the secondary shock is negligible. Moreover, the boundary layer shows a relatively small contribution to the overall losses; however, it is noteworthy that the presented LES considers (1) adiabatic walls, thus no purely thermal boundary layer is present in the domain, and (2) a logarithmic law-of-the-wall model with a non-zero velocity at the first wall node. These simplifications limit the magnitude of gradients and consequently losses in the boundary layer.

FIG. 24. Relative contribution of volume-integrated entropy generation terms by regions of interest (BL = boundary layer, Sec. Shock = secondary shock, Sep. = diffuser-induced separation).

The analysis by loss mechanism and by region of interest now allows an identification of viable performance improvement strategies. Minimizing entropy generation can be achieved by a reduction in gradients, thus, an increase in secondary flow temperature with respect to the primary flow may reduce the thermal losses generated in the shear layer to a first order. Viscous dissipation losses in the shear layer may be minimized by increasing the secondary flow velocity to a first order. This reduction may be equally achieved by reducing the secondary flow rate \dot{m}_{14} , hence reducing ω ; a conclusion coherent with literature²⁰. To a second order, separation in the diffuser and other loss sources may be mitigated by a geometrically optimized design.

3. Turbine Inlet Flow Characteristics

With the global and local performance analysis conducted in previous sections, the potential of an ejector integrated with an RDC has been assessed and possible performance improvement strategies have been pointed out. However, the presence of the axial turbine downstream of the ejector imposes constraints on the ejector exit flow characteristics, which have not yet been addressed. In the following, the relevant section in the ejector to examine the turbine inlet flow is at station 41, as indicated in Fig. 1.

Subsonic axial turbine optimum efficiency is attained for a statistically steady, axial flow with a Mach number in the low subsonic range⁵⁴. Figure 25 shows the instantaneous, area-averaged Mach number in the turbine inlet plane, M_{41} . The Mach number fluctuations are between roughly 0.25 and 0.37, with a time-averaged value of 0.293. The results show some slight variations in peak amplitudes, which are investigated in more detail in a dedicated unsteadiness analysis. The impact of a transient Mach number at a frequency in the kHz range has not yet been thoroughly addressed in literature; further studies are necessary to determine the effect of such fluctuations on turbine operation. The time-averaged Mach number in the low subsonic regime is favorable for turbine integration although it is higher than the values typically stated (e.g. 0.15⁵⁴). It is recalled here that several studies recently presented optimized subsonic turbine vanes able to ingest flow up to Mach 1^{13,14}.

FIG. 25. Instantaneous, area-averaged Mach number M_{41} at the turbine inlet.

In addition to the Mach number, the absolute total temperature, as well as its spatial distri-

bution are of significance for turbine efficiency and operation⁵⁸. The spatial distribution of total temperature is characterized using the Total Temperature Distortion Factor (TTDF)⁵⁸,

$$TTDF = \frac{T_{t,max} - T_{t,min}}{T_{t,mean}} \Big|_{41}, \quad (16)$$

where the indices *max* and *min* refer to the spatial maximum and minimum T_t ; the denominator is the massflow-averaged total temperature. For a transient flow, the value of TTDF is time-dependent. Although several metrics exist to estimate the spatial non-uniformity of the total temperature in the combustor exit patch⁵⁹, for simplicity, only the quantity defined in Eq. 16 is retained as a first approximation. In Fig. 26, the instantaneous TTDF and the respective minimum and maximum total temperatures are displayed. Evidently, the upper limit of the order of 1800 K for T_{t41} ⁹ is well respected, and a considerably higher T_{t41} is desirable in the future to decrease *sfc*. The value of TTDF never exceeds 0.1, with a time-averaged value of 0.081. Such total temperature distortion is coherent with values obtained in literature⁵⁹. The instantaneous contours of TTDF show a variation between approximately 0.062 and 0.095, corresponding to an amplitude of roughly $\pm 20\%$. The effect of a time-dependent TTDF in the kHz range on turbine efficiency has rarely been considered; its definitive effect remains to be determined in future analyses. However, the time-averaged outcome is promising and reinforces the compatibility between ejector and axial turbine.

As pointed out previously, unsteady inflow is generally considered detrimental for turbine operation¹², thus, another objective of the ejector is to dampen the fluctuations in total pressure stemming from the RDC exhaust before the flow is admitted into the turbine. The time dependent parameter $D = (P_{t,max} - P_{t,min})/P_{t,mean}$ allows to formulate the ejector total pressure dampening ξ_{P_t} ¹⁵,

$$\xi_{P_t} = \frac{D_4 - D_{41}}{D_4}, \quad (17)$$

where D is extracted at the RDC exhaust, station 4, and at the turbine inlet, station 41. The indices *min*, *max* and *mean* refer to time, i.e. D is evaluated along one or multiple fluctuation periods and the minimum, maximum and average values are extracted. To reduce P_t to a single value in each plane, massflow-averaging is employed.

Figure 27 compares total pressure at the RDC exit and the turbine inlet. The total pressure P_{t4} has deviated from the sinusoidal characteristic imposed at 4' by passing through the converging-

FIG. 26. Instantaneous maximum and minimum turbine inlet total temperature T_{t41} , and the associated Total Temperature Distortion Factor TTDF.

diverging nozzle; seemingly being composed of multiple harmonics. Such characteristics have also been observed in other studies focusing on unsteady nozzle behavior⁴⁷. At the turbine inlet, P_{t41} shows a similar characteristic with multiple harmonics. The first harmonic at the imposed pulsation frequency of 8 kHz, however, seems to remain unaffected throughout the domain, and only the amplitude of the fluctuations is reduced. Averaged over 24 single periods, the dampening of P_t through the ejector amounted to $\xi_{P_t} = 65\%$. At the turbine inlet, total pressure fluctuates with approximately $\pm 10\%$ from its mean value.

The specific frequency content of both flows has been analyzed by a Fast Fourier Transform which is shown in Fig. 28. Indeed, the first harmonic at 8 kHz is recovered, with several additional harmonics visible in both RDC exit and turbine inlet signal. Furthermore, the frequency spectrum between the peaks at the main harmonics seems to be more pronounced in the turbine inlet than in the RDC exit signal, as evident in the zoomed view at the top right of Fig. 28. The results are qualitatively in line with findings from a previous study of an ejector under unsteady inflow, where temperature and gas composition effects of the RDC exhaust were neglected¹⁹. Paxson and Dougherty¹⁷ investigated a pulsejet and ejector coupled system, and found a dampening of pressure fluctuations through the ejector by an order of magnitude. Considering that total pressure

FIG. 27. Instantaneous, massflow-averaged RDC exit total pressure P_{t4} and the turbine inlet total pressure P_{t41} , both normalized by their time-averaged values.

fluctuation amplitudes at the turbine inlet in a Brayton engine may amount to approximately $\pm 5\text{--}7\%$ from their mean value⁶⁰, the turbine inlet flow total pressure is considered admissible for turbine integration. It is hence concluded that the dampening characteristics of the ejector facilitate the integration of an RDC in a turbomachinery application.

FIG. 28. Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) of the instantaneous, massflow-averaged RDC exit total pressure P_{t4} and the turbine inlet total pressure P_{t41} , both normalized by their time-averaged values.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

A numerical analysis based on Large-Eddy Simulation (LES) of a conventional tubular ejector configuration under pulsed inflow, representative of rotating detonation combustor (RDC) exhaust gas conditions, was conducted. RDC exhaust flow characteristics were generated by a suitable choice of inlet pulsation amplitude and frequency. Total pressure, total temperature and reduced flow rates showed a sufficient agreement with RDC exhaust gas characteristics available in literature.

A dynamic flow field analysis revealed the presence of a permanent secondary shock located at the end of the constant-area mixing section. Along the jet centerline, a Mach number in the low supersonic regime was observed. The axial velocity profiles throughout the mixing chamber showed significant asymmetry at early mixing stages and aligned relatively well towards the end of the mixing chamber where the secondary shock is located. Mixing occurs rapidly downstream of the confluence of primary and secondary flow, and is terminated slightly upstream of the constant-area mixing chamber exit.

The specific fuel consumption of the system of RDC and ejector was 30% above and the pressure gain was approximately 85% below a reference cycle without ejector. The relatively low global performance is due to the operating conditions and ejector geometry that were not specifically optimized. A significant influence of the RDC exhaust flow unsteadiness on instantaneous pressure gain was asserted. A subsequent loss analysis based on entropy generation pointed out several areas of possible improvement. Heat conduction losses had the most significant influence (64.3%), followed by viscous dissipation (33.4%); species diffusion losses were negligible (2.3%). In order to identify possible design and operating condition targets for loss reduction, the entropy generation terms were subsequently integrated in different regions. The analysis revealed that the most significant contribution to the overall loss budget originates in the shear layer. The diffuser-induced separation and the boundary layer contributed only to viscous dissipation losses, although to a much smaller extent than the shear layer. The influence of the secondary shock is found negligible. To reduce losses in the shear layer, increasing secondary flow temperature and velocity or decreasing the entrainment ratio could be useful measures.

At the turbine inlet, the mean Mach number and the averaged total temperature distortion TTDF were deemed suitable, with values of 0.293 and 0.081, respectively. However, both showed residual fluctuations from the RDC exhaust, whose impact is to be determined in future analyses. An

unsteadiness analysis revealed that 65% of total pressure fluctuations at the RDC exhaust are dampened through the ejector, which favors turbine integration. The remaining total pressure fluctuations at the turbine inlet were approximately 10%. The main oscillation frequency was unchanged, although the signal was distributed over a wider range of harmonics.

The flow conditions obtained at the turbine inlet underline the potential of integrating an RDC with an ejector. A consideration of the azimuthal components of the RDC exhaust in the future may reveal further insight into RDC - ejector coupling. Moreover, future work should include a dedicated design study of an annular ejector, utilizing the areas of improvement pointed out in this work. With such an approach, both global performance and local loss generation are expected to improve, while the dampening and turbine inlet flow characteristics may be retained.

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

REFERENCES

- ¹M. Asli, P. Stathopoulos, and C. O. Paschereit, "Aerodynamic investigation of guide vane configurations downstream a rotating detonation combustor," *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power* **143**, 061011 (2021).
- ²V. Anand and E. Gutmark, "Rotating detonation combustors and their similarities to rocket instabilities," *Progress in Energy and Combustion Science* **73**, 182–234 (2019).
- ³B. A. Rankin, J. Hoke, and F. Schauer, "Periodic exhaust flow through a converging-diverging nozzle downstream of a rotating detonation engine," in *AIAA SciTech Forum*, 2014-1015 (2014).

- ⁴I. V. Walters, R. M. Gejji, S. D. Heister, and C. D. Slabaugh, “Flow and performance analysis of a natural gas-air rotating detonation engine with high-speed velocimetry,” *Combustion and Flame* **232**, 111549 (2021).
- ⁵S. Talukdar, D. Langner, A. Gupta, and A. K. Agrawal, “Flow field measurements across convergent nozzles of a rotating detonation combustor using high-speed PIV,” in *AIAA SciTech Forum*, 2024-0602 (2024).
- ⁶A. Naples, J. Hoke, and F. Schauer, “Rotating detonation engine interaction with an annular ejector,” in *AIAA SciTech Forum*, 2014-0287 (2014).
- ⁷R. Klopsch, N. Garan, M. Bohon, E. Bach, M. Asli, and P. Stathopoulos, “2D euler modeling of rotating detonation combustion in preparation for turbomachinery matching,” in *AIAA SciTech Forum*, 2022-0836 (2022).
- ⁸T. A. Kaemming and D. E. Paxson, “Determining the pressure gain of pressure gain combustion,” in *2018 Joint Propulsion Conference*, 2018-4567 (2018).
- ⁹D. G. Wilson and T. Korakianitis, *The Design of High-Efficiency Turbomachinery and Gas Turbines*, 2nd ed. (MIT Press, 2014).
- ¹⁰Z. Liu, J. Braun, and G. Paniagua, “Performance of axial turbines exposed to large fluctuations,” in *AIAA/SAE/ASME Joint Propulsion Conference*, 2017-4817 (Atlanta, USA, 2017).
- ¹¹S. P. Lynch and M. Boggio, “Computational analysis of rotating detonation engine exhaust interacting with a turbine vane,” in *AIAA SciTech Forum*, 2022-1720 (2022).
- ¹²A. S. George, R. Driscoll, E. Gutmark, and D. Munday, “Experimental comparison of axial turbine performance under steady and pulsating flows,” *Journal of Turbomachinery* **136**, 111005 (2014).
- ¹³Z. Liu, J. Braun, and G. Paniagua, “Thermal power plant upgrade via a rotating detonation combustor and retrofitted turbine with optimized endwalls,” *International Journal of Mechanical Sciences* **188**, 105918 (2020).
- ¹⁴S. Grasa and G. Paniagua, “Design, multi-point optimization and analysis of diffusive stator vanes to enable turbine integration into rotating detonation engines,” in *ASME Turbo Expo: Power for Land, Sea, and Air*, GT2023-101726 (2023).
- ¹⁵Z. Liu, J. Braun, and G. Paniagua, “Characterization of a supersonic turbine downstream of a rotating detonation combustor,” *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power* **141**, 031501 (2019).

- ¹⁶N. Mushtaq, G. Colella, and P. Gaetani, “Design and parametric analysis of a supersonic turbine for rotating detonation engine applications,” *International Journal of Turbomachinery, Propulsion and Power* **7**, 1 (2022).
- ¹⁷D. Paxson and K. Dougherty, “Ejector enhanced pulsejet based pressure gain combustors: An old idea with a new twist,” in *AIAA/ASME/SAE/ASEE Joint Propulsion Conference*, 2005-4216 (2005).
- ¹⁸D. E. Paxson and A. Naples, “Numerical and analytical assessment of a coupled rotating detonation engine and turbine experiment,” in *AIAA SciTech Forum*, 2017-1746 (2017).
- ¹⁹G. Uhl, S. Taileb, S. Zurbach, N. Odier, T. Poinso, and M. Bellenoue, “Phenomenological aerodynamic analysis of an ejector exposed to large inlet pulsations,” *Journal of Propulsion and Power*, 1–12 (2024).
- ²⁰Z. Ji, H. Zhang, and B. Wang, “Performance analysis of dual-duct rotating detonation aeroturbine engine,” *Aerospace Science and Technology* **92**, 806–819 (2019).
- ²¹L. Qi, N. Zhao, Z. Wang, J. Yang, and H. Zheng, “Pressure gain characteristic of continuously rotating detonation combustion and its influence on gas turbine cycle performance,” *IEEE Access* **6**, 70236–70247 (2018).
- ²²T. Schonfeld and M. Rudgyard, “Steady and unsteady flow simulations using the hybrid flow solver AVBP,” *AIAA Journal* **37**, 1378–1385 (1999).
- ²³F. M. White, *Viscous Fluid Flow*, 2nd ed. (McGraw Hill, 1992).
- ²⁴J. O. Hirschfelder, C. F. Curtiss, and R. B. Bird, *The Molecular Theory of Gases and Liquids* (John Wiley & Sons, 1964).
- ²⁵P. Boivin, C. Jiménez, A. Sánchez, and F. Williams, “An explicit reduced mechanism for H₂–air combustion,” *Proceedings of the Combustion Institute* **33**, 517–523 (2011).
- ²⁶D. R. Stull and H. Prophet, “Joint Army-Navy-Air Force (JANAF) Thermochemical Tables,” Tech. Rep. NBS37 (National Standard Reference Data System, 1971).
- ²⁷F. Nicoud and F. Ducros, “Subgrid-scale stress modelling based on the square of the velocity gradient tensor,” *Flow, Turbulence and Combustion* **62**, 183–200 (1999).
- ²⁸S. Croquer, O. Lamberts, S. Poncet, S. Moreau, and Y. Bartosiewicz, “Large Eddy Simulation of a supersonic air ejector,” *Applied Thermal Engineering* **209**, 118177 (2022).
- ²⁹J. Hoste, S. Fechter, S. Karl, and K. Hannemann, “Study of a supersonic reacting wall jet with a variable turbulent Prandtl and Schmidt number approach,” *Aerospace Science and Technology* **106**, 106070 (2020).

- ³⁰O. Colin and M. Rudgyard, “Development of high-order Taylor–Galerkin schemes for LES,” *Journal of Computational Physics* **162**, 338–371 (2000).
- ³¹O. Colin, *Simulations Aux Grandes Echelles De La Combustion Turbulente Premelangee Dans Les Statoreacteurs*, Ph.D. thesis, Institute National Polytechnique, Toulouse, France (2000).
- ³²A. W. Cook and W. H. Cabot, “A high-wavenumber viscosity for high-resolution numerical methods,” *Journal of Computational Physics* **195**, 594–601 (2004).
- ³³P. Schmitt, T. Poinso, B. Schuermans, and K. P. Geigle, “Large-Eddy Simulation and experimental study of heat transfer, nitric oxide emissions and combustion instability in a swirled turbulent high-pressure burner,” *Journal of Fluid Mechanics* **570**, 17–46 (2007).
- ³⁴J. Kracik and V. Dvorak, “Secondary flow choking in axisymmetric supersonic air ejector with adjustable motive nozzle,” *Applied Thermal Engineering* **204**, 117936 (2022).
- ³⁵T. Poinso and S. K. Lele, “Boundary conditions for direct simulations of compressible viscous flows,” *Journal of Computational Physics* **101**, 104–129 (1992).
- ³⁶N. Odier, M. Sanjosé, L. Gicquel, T. Poinso, S. Moreau, and F. Duchaine, “A characteristic inlet boundary condition for compressible, turbulent, multispecies, turbomachinery flows,” *Computers and Fluids* **178**, 41–55 (2019).
- ³⁷V. Granet, O. Vermorel, T. Léonard, L. Gicquel, and T. Poinso, “Comparison of nonreflecting outlet boundary conditions for compressible solvers on unstructured grids,” *AIAA Journal* **48**, 2348–2364 (2010).
- ³⁸G. Daviller, G. Oztarlik, and T. Poinso, “A generalized non-reflecting inlet boundary condition for steady and forced compressible flows with injection of vortical and acoustic waves,” *Computers and Fluids* **190**, 503–513 (2019).
- ³⁹P. Strempl, O. Dounia, D. Laera, and T. Poinso, “Effects of mixing assumptions and models for LES of hydrogen-fueled rotating detonation engines,” *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* **62**, 1–16 (2024).
- ⁴⁰N. Mushtaq and P. Gaetani, “The effect of upstream unsteadiness on the unstarting of a supersonic inlet turbine,” in *ASME Turbo Expo: Power for Land, Sea, and Air*, GT2023-103883 (2023).
- ⁴¹P. C. Nassini, A. Andreini, and M. D. Bohon, “Characterization of refill region and mixing state immediately ahead of a hydrogen-air rotating detonation using LES,” *Combustion and Flame* **258**, 113050 (2023).

- ⁴²G. Wang, F. Duchaine, D. Papadogiannis, I. Duran, S. Moreau, and L. Y. Gicquel, “An overset grid method for large eddy simulation of turbomachinery stages,” *Journal of Computational Physics* **274**, 333–355 (2014).
- ⁴³E. Garnier, N. Adams, and P. Sagaut, *Large-Eddy simulation for compressible flows* (Springer Science & Business Media, 2009).
- ⁴⁴J. U. Schlüter, “Influence of axisymmetric assumptions on Large Eddy Simulations of a confined jet and a swirl flow,” *International Journal of Computational Fluid Dynamics* **18**, 235–245 (2004).
- ⁴⁵I. Celik, M. Klein, and J. Janicka, “Assessment measures for engineering LES applications,” *Journal of Fluids Engineering* **131**, 031102 (2009).
- ⁴⁶S. B. Pope, “Ten questions concerning the Large-Eddy Simulation of turbulent flows,” *New Journal of Physics* **6**, 35 (2004).
- ⁴⁷D. A. Schwer, C. M. Brophy, and R. H. Kelso, “Pressure characteristics of an aerospike nozzle in a rotating detonation engine,” in *2018 Joint Propulsion Conference*, 2018-4968 (2018).
- ⁴⁸A. H. Shapiro, *The Dynamics and Thermodynamics of Compressible Fluid Flows*, Vol. 1 (John Wiley & Sons, 1953).
- ⁴⁹E. Bach, M. Bohon, C. O. Paschereit, and P. Stathopoulos, “Development of an instrumented guide vane set for RDC exhaust flow characterization,” in *2018 Joint Propulsion Conference*, 2018-4479 (2018).
- ⁵⁰P. Borgohain, D. Choudhary, A. Dalal, and G. Natarajan, “Numerical investigation of mixing enhancement for multi-species flows in wavy channels,” *Chemical Engineering and Processing-Process Intensification* **127**, 191–205 (2018).
- ⁵¹A. H. Lefebvre and D. R. Ballal, *Gas Turbine Combustion: Alternative Fuels and Emissions*, 3rd ed. (CRC Press, 2010).
- ⁵²A. Arbel, A. Shklyar, D. Hershal, M. Barak, and M. Sokolov, “Ejector irreversibility characteristics,” *Journal of Fluids Engineering* **125**, 121–129 (2003).
- ⁵³E. Bach, C. Paschereit, P. Stathopoulos, and M. D. Bohon, “An empirical model for stagnation pressure gain in rotating detonation combustors,” *Proceedings of the Combustion Institute* **38**, 3807–3814 (2021).
- ⁵⁴J. Sousa, G. Paniagua, and E. C. Morata, “Thermodynamic analysis of a gas turbine engine with a rotating detonation combustor,” *Applied Energy* **195**, 247–256 (2017).

- ⁵⁵A. Sciacovelli, V. Verda, and E. Sciubba, “Entropy generation analysis as a design tool — a review,” *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* **43**, 1167–1181 (2015).
- ⁵⁶J. Sierra-Pallares, J. G. Del Valle, P. G. Carrascal, and F. C. Ruiz, “A computational study about the types of entropy generation in three different R134a ejector mixing chambers,” *International Journal of Refrigeration* **63**, 199–213 (2016).
- ⁵⁷M. Harnieh, N. Odier, J. Dombard, F. Duchaine, and L. Gicquel, “Loss predictions in the high-pressure film-cooled turbine vane of the FACTOR project by means of wall-modeled Large Eddy simulation,” in *ASME Turbo Expo: Power for Land, Sea, and Air*, GT2020-14232 (2020).
- ⁵⁸S. Salvadori, F. Montomoli, F. Martelli, K. S. Chana, I. Qureshi, and T. Povey, “Analysis on the effect of a nonuniform inlet profile on heat transfer and fluid flow in turbine stages,” *Journal of Turbomachinery* **134**, 011012 (2011).
- ⁵⁹T. Povey, K. S. Chana, T. V. Jones, and J. Hurrion, “The effect of hot-streaks on HP vane surface and endwall heat transfer: An experimental and numerical study,” *Journal of Turbomachinery* **129**, 32–43 (2005).
- ⁶⁰S. Southworth, M. Dunn, C. Haldeman, J.-P. Chen, G. Heitland, and J. Liu, “Time-accurate predictions for a fully cooled high-pressure turbine stage—Part I: comparison of predictions with data,” *Journal of Turbomachinery* **131**, 031003 (2009).